

Preventing a Civilizational Collapse With The Help of The Free Energy Principle

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Abstract

As Niels Bohr said, “Prediction is very difficult, especially if it’s about the future,” but at the same time, we can’t help ourselves, because anticipation is one of the fundamental functions of our internal model—perhaps even its most fundamental function. While our survival is the *raison d’être* of both anticipation and our internal model.

What is difficult to actualize is our collective anticipation coupled with our collective action aimed at our collective survival.

Unlike our own internal model, which is embodied within us and emerges naturally, a collective internal model, in order to emerge, must be individually wanted by agents who decide to establish an organization capable of embodying it. It is a difficult but crucial step: the transition from individual wills to a common will. It is this kind of organization that this paper seeks to model and create, drawing inspiration from the free energy principle.

Modeling our collective survival requires identifying what threatens it. A task that depends closely on our reading of the world and our reading of History. According to my reading, the main threat to our collective survival lies in ideologies and the degenerative dynamic system that emerges from their rivalry. The natural emergence of ideologies stems directly from the minimization of surprise and the Darwinian propensity for control. Indeed, by confining its community within a deceptive dark-room, an ideology controls the beliefs of its community unbeknownst to it.

Since ideological control over beliefs constitutes an invisible constraint, and since freedom is understood as the absence of constraints, our freedom—both individual and collective—depends on the knowledge we have, individually and collectively, of this control.

To help us understand how ideologies hijack our freedom, we will distinguish between the decision-maker, that chooses options, and the set of options from which he can choose.

Finally, we will draw on the distinction between shared knowledge and common knowledge to determine the criteria under which the organization’s internal model can be rightly considered the common consciousness of its members.

Anticipation of the Future

Our anticipation of the future depends on our reading of the current state of the world and our reading of History, which in turn depends on our conception of the world and our conceptual tools whose acquisition depends on us and on the richness or poverty of our conceptual environment.

A civilizational collapse, much like the collapse of a building, would be a sudden event, once it would start to collapse, it would be already too late to stop it. We must prevent it. There may be warning signs, which become obvious in hindsight but which we ignored because we lacked the proper script ([Albarracin](#)). What is fairly certain, however, is that a civilization, like a building, will eventually collapse if its foundations are continuously undermined.

The Parts of the Plan

The plan, like a jigsaw puzzle without its image on the box, comprises several interconnected parts that must be presented one by one before making sense.

1. The field of action.

The field of action is that of ideas, beliefs (including values), theories, conceptions of the world, paradigms taking place in our cultural environment, which takes place in our ecological niche.

1.1. Using the materials provided by language, our species has built our econiche by adding, on top of its concrete base, an abstract intersubjective layer mainly structured by a tangle of institutions (e.g., money, states, ideologies, armies, ...)

2. The temporal scale of action.

The current state of our econiche and its abstract layer, which includes our conceptual and cultural environment, depends on its path stretching back hundreds of thousands of years. Because of its path dependency, we cannot change its current state, but we could change its future states if we knew how. This means that the scale of the action would be intergenerational.

3. The first step would be to create a new type of institution that would enable us to act in concert on the abstract layer of the econiche. Drawing on the distinction between common knowledge and shared knowledge, the institution's internal model would be designed to serve as the common consciousness of its members. I will elaborate on this concept further on.

3.1. One of the fundamental issues that must be kept in mind is that power tends to concentrate while knowledge is distributed.

4. The possibility of a civilizational collapse implies that there has been civilizational progress (not to be conflated with technological progress). I will argue that it consists of the progress of freedom which does not follow a smooth upward trajectory. Rather, it is

embodied by conceptual innovations that have freed the society by resolving crises (dominant negative narratives) that were stifling it. Nowadays, those gains, which form the bedrock of our civilization, are being dangerously undermined by ideologies.

Hence, the centrality of the conceptualization of freedom and the relevance of the free energy principle which provides a scientific explanation of it, as opposed to the scientific myth of the illusion of freedom.

Conceptualization of Our Freedom

1. Our conception of freedom conditions our freedom, because if we misunderstand freedom, we cannot know to what extent we are free. And if we don't know to what extent we are not free, freeing ourselves cannot be an option.
2. Our freedom and our consciousness, which is part of our internal model, coexist and they both depend on our body and our health.

2.1. The Concept of Consciousness

Our consciousness can be seen as a product of natural selection, just like our legs and our eyes. Like all the other faculties we have inherited, it developed because it conferred an adaptive advantage on our distant ancestors. However, there is an important distinction. Our consciousness—that is, the faculty that allows us to be conscious—must be distinguished from being conscious of what we are conscious of, just as we distinguish our legs from walking.

Our consciousness allows us to be aware of what we are aware of, but it only allows it. This implies that being aware is not necessarily effortless nor automatic. Because sometimes we are mistaken and we can be misled.

However, unlike our legs and our eyes, our consciousness is not tangible nor material, even though its existence depends on our brain and body. So, if it is immaterial and intangible, what exactly can it be made of?

It can be shown that it is an abstract entity.

- 2.2. To apprehend the relation between our freedom and our consciousness, we will distinguish the set of options that we could choose, at the present moment, from the decision-maker who, at each moment of our waking state, chooses different options. In order to highlight the fact that this set has a structure, we will call it our freedom space. The decision-maker and the freedom space are not really distinct. We distinguish them abstractly to help us conceptualize our freedom and the relation between our freedom and our consciousness.

3. Our freedom space depends, among other things, on our physical, cultural, and conceptual environment.
 - 3.1. Our freedom space depends not only on the options offered to us by our environment, it also depends on our knowledge of those options, the acquisition of which is under the charge of our consciousness.
4. Our freedom space is path dependent. It can shrink or, on the contrary, expand, depending on the options we choose.
5. One of the conditions of freedom is the absence of constraints (this is a tricky one). Distinguishing between the decision-maker and the freedom space allows us to distinguish different types of constraints.
 - 5.1. Those of which we are aware: we would like to choose an option, but a manifest coercive force prevents us from doing so, e.g., we are in jail.
 - 5.2. Constraints that we chose, e.g., those imposed by the decision to become a parent.
 - 5.3. Institutional constraints, e.g., paying a fine.
 - 5.4. And constraints of which we cannot be aware, because, unbeknownst to us, options we could have chosen have been removed from our environment. Namely, from our cultural and conceptual environments whose configuration has been strongly conditioned by the Darwinian propensity for control. In such cases, when constraints are invisible, we could be much less free than we believe we are.

Control

“The primary dynamic that has driven and is currently driving human evolution is competition with other people and groups of other people for resource control, including control of the behavior of other people.

My argument is that the foci of control-related behavioral biases and the supporting brain, perceptual, cognitive, and affective systems are three general forms of resource: social, biological, and physical. The corresponding competencies are captured by the domains of folk psychology (...), folk biology (...), and folk physics (...). When applied to humans, these domains refer to an inherent and intuitive understanding of other people (folk psychology), other species (folk biology), and the physical world (folk physics). When meshed with ecological dominance and a struggle with other people to control these ecologies, the result is an evolutionary arms race. An arms race refers to the evolutionary change that results from the competing interests of individuals, within or between species, as they attempt to achieve competitive advantage.” Geary

There are different ways to control other people’s behavior. Violence and fear are widespread, but the best collective way is to control their beliefs unbeknownst to them. This kind of control can be achieved through lies or beliefs shaping the cultural environment, especially beliefs rooted in the affect. When a belief system usurps agents’ freedom, the milieu instilling it will often exhibit what Hannah Arendt called automatic processes, i.e., a kind of local determinism.

“It is in the nature of the automatic processes to which man is subject,
but within and against which he can assert himself through action,
that they can only spell ruin to human life.”

Arendt 1

The question that begs to be asked is: who is in control within an ideological econiche? However, this is not quite the right question, because History is partly in control. This kind of control from beyond the grave requires a community that is captive to a closed cultural environment, a dark-room, conceptually impoverished so that nobody questions their beliefs, at least publicly.

Let's take the example of the high path-dependent conflict in the Middle East. It is the historical dimension of its causal structure which brings the closure into the present. That closure is prolonged into the future by the present where lies the freedom to change the course of History toward a future with incommensurably less suffering (a substantive principle of the plan [Ramstead](#)). They are collectively prisoners of History.

Nowadays, this closure is achieved by ideologies, which are institutions that erect dark-rooms to minimize surprise ([Friston 1](#)) within which communities lock themselves away.

An ideology goes with a closed misconception of the world.

Conceptions of the World

Our conception of the world is part of our internal model. The free energy principle implies that although we physically live in the physical world, mentally, we live in the world of our conception of the world. This entails that we mentally inhabit different worlds to the extent that our conceptions of the world diverge.

When I first became interested in the free energy principle, I assumed that the *raison d'être* of the part of our internal model pointing outward was to model the world as it is. But that is not the case. I believe that the *raison d'être* of our internal model is survival, and what the part pointing outward models is rather our action on the outside world. Yet, this action may well involve denying certain aspects of the outside world in order to act and minimize surprise within the controlled part of the econiche.

This is precisely what ideological misconceptions of the world are doing. For human beings, their survival, their security, and their future depend on belonging to a community. And for an ideological community, this belonging requires embracing what the community considers to be the truth.

So there are two opposing survival strategies: shape the controlled sub-econiche to match the dogmas of the model, or try modeling the world as it is. But the latter is doomed to be outclassed by the former if it remains confined to isolated individuals, regardless of their number, if they cannot find the means to organize and unite to act in concert at the level of the econiche, as ideological communities do.

THE ANALOGY WITH GEOMETRIES

There is an instructive analogy between geometries and conceptions of the world.

A geometry depends on two things, its coherence and its axioms. For instance, when the fifth axiom states that through a point outside a line there passes more than one parallel, in a two-dimensional space, we obtain a [hyperbolic geometry](#) where the sum of the angles of a triangle is less than 180° and where the shortest path between two points is not straight, but curved.

The analogy is based on the idea that, like geometry, the beliefs of a conception of the world are of two types: fundamental beliefs that are based on facts, presuppositions, or postulates, and beliefs that are inferred or deduced from the formers. For instance, the existence of God is a postulate that leads to belief in a form of supernatural magic. The opposite of this postulate is the refusal to believe in the existence of supernatural magic, which entails to not believing in God.

However, there is a fundamental difference. While coherence is an existence condition for a geometry, it is the (mental) existence of the agent that is the existence condition for his conception of the world. It is a practical condition. A naive agent can be trapped in a community of beliefs and lack the conceptual tools to be able to choose epistemic coherence. Or he might reject epistemic coherence for instrumental reasons.

Markov Blankets of Our Econiche

Let's define the proximity between two agents in terms of what their conceptions of the world have in common, particularly with regard to polarizing political subjects and our collective future. This distance structures the set of agents, distributing them in a metric space whose path-dependent transformation has been strongly conditioned by the propensity for controlling beliefs. However, the propensity for control can take two opposite forms: controlling others in order to avoid being controlled by them, and not being controlled by others without controlling them.¹

By adding a degree of conviction to this metric—how far one would go to defend his conception of the world—this distance establishes the shape of the space. The ideological agglomerations thus formed meet the conditions for constituting an intermediate level between the micro-level of agents and the econiche macro-level. By filtering and interpreting afferent information in a way that corroborates its dogmas, an ideological community forms a Markov blanket that acts to configure the world in its own way.

Note that the greater the distance between two agents' conceptions of the world, the more their worlds diverge and the less likely they are to agree.

To give an idea of the configuration of the field of action, we will restrict our Markov blanket to the left-right opposition, and extend a metaphor introduced by Steven Pinker.

¹ Not being controlled by others without controlling them is what Athenian thinkers were looking for when they invented democracy. See: [Arendt 1](#).

“I sometimes refer to the mythical place called the Left Pole. Now just as when you’re at the North Pole all directions are south, the Left Pole is a mythical spot from which all directions are right so any opinion that does not conform to this orthodoxy is branded as right-wing opinion.”²

[Pinker](#)

The Left Pole suggests a diametrically opposed Right Pole where all directions point to the left. Both have all the answers, so there is no need to argue. On the left, they know who are the good guys and who are the evildoers. On the right, they know who should dominate and who should be dominated. But on the left as much as on the right, they ignore that they are locked inside informational enclosures, in other words, inside dark-rooms.

Unfortunately, with the rise of social media and their algorithms, the cognitive enclosures of these dark-rooms have been industrially heightened and solidified.

All that remains is to place on a globe the right and left polar caps inhabited by their respective communities, whose conviction diminishes in intensity as they move away from the Pole and toward the equatorial band. Within this band are those whose conception of the world remains open and who, consciously or not, seek to apprehend the world as it is. This does not mean that they are immune to ideologies. No one is. Ideological lies can be very subtle and convincing.

Some information can be extracted from this sketch.

1. Attacking only one side is counterproductive. Not only because it plays into the hands of the opposite side, but also because it solidifies the community under attack, which will react by closing ranks. As Berger and Luckmann put it: “Any group engaged in social conflict requires solidarity. Ideologies generate solidarity.” [Berger & Luckmann](#).
2. The equatorial band does not offer what polar caps offer. It does not constitute an entity capable of acting on the econiche. Unlike agents who adhere to an ideology, the agents that make up the equatorial band do not form a community and do not really share a common world, since they lack a common conception of the world. Communication between any two agents is restricted to the overlap between their conceptions of the world, without them knowing exactly what exactly is overlapping, if they don’t make the effort to find out. A situation that can lead to misunderstandings and distortions.
3. The equatorial band has the faults that go with its qualities. Its inhabitants are sovereign, but their sovereignty entails that they are historically insignificant.

² It is worth recalling what Hannah Arendt said about the existential relation between the left and the right: “Both liberalism and conservatism were born in this climate of violently oscillating public opinion, and they are tied together, not only because each would lose its very substance without the presence of its opponent in the field of theory and ideology, but because both are primarily concerned with restoration, with restoring either freedom or authority, or the relationship between both, to its traditional position. It is in this sense that they form the two sides of the same coin, just as their progress-or-doom ideologies correspond to the two possible directions of the historical process as such; if one assumes, as both do, that there is such a thing as a historical process with a definable direction and a predictable end, it obviously can land us only in paradise or in hell.” [Arendt 3](#).

Institutions

Douglas Cecil North has established that :

“The study of institutions and institutional change necessitates as a first requirement the conceptual separation of institutions from organizations. Institutions are the rules of the game and organizations are the players. The interaction between the two shapes institutional change. Institutions are the constraints that human beings impose on human interaction. They consist of formal rules (constitutions, statute law, common law, regulations) and informal constraints (conventions, norms and self-enforced codes of conduct) and their enforcement characteristics.
[...]

Organizations consist of groups of individuals bound together by some common objectives.”

North

Ideologies

The word “ideology” has several meanings. Here, an ideology is the equivalent of a malevolent lie transposed to the collective scale, to the scale of the conception of the world and to the scale of History. It is a dogmatic misconception of the world, made up of hypostatized false theories generating a partly imaginary common world, a dark-room, within which the community that embodies it locks itself. It seeks to impose itself to the rest of the world and tends toward totalitarianism.

Ideologies are not fixed; they adapt in order to survive. For instance, in the last 40 years, the left has shifted from Marxist dogmatism to identity dogmatism.

Before the emergence of social media, ideologies were not institutions in the *Northian* sense. They lacked the “organized” condition. They were more like movements. But with their algorithms that organize them based on similarity of beliefs, social media have transformed these movements into institutions.

The agents of an ideological community follow unspoken rules. They must defend and promote their common conception of the world without ever questioning it. They must agree to [suspend their disbelief](#) and seek to configure the world as prescribed by the ideology.

There is also a decisive trait common to all ideologies apart from scientism.³ An ideology always has a clearly identified enemy, a “them” regarded as essentially inferior, despised, dehumanized. An ideology thus takes on, but in an imaginary way, the non-imaginary form of *us-against-them* of our distant and not-so-distant ancestors. Furthermore, even though ideologies clash with one another to impose their dogmas, together they form a dynamic system that not only reinforces dogmatism but, fueled by their mutual contempt, could quickly degenerate and lead to the dreaded collapse.

³ The scientific ideology is an exception: its adherents are not organized, and they don't have enemies. Although smugness replaces contempt and is used to exert social control, I see no reason to call it malevolent. However, scientism is harmful because it undermines the conceptual tools that constitute science.

INSTITUTIONAL LIES

Ideological dogmas are institutional lies. Even though those lies could be beneficial at the individual level—i.g., believing in God can be anxietytic—they are often harmful at the collective level (wars of religion). Furthermore, not only each of us is powerless in the face of institutional lies, but their accumulation destroy the means we have to navigate the world.

“...the result of a consistent and total substitution of lies for factual truth is not that the lies will now be accepted as truth, and the truth be defamed as lies, but that the sense by which we take our bearings in the real world—and the category of truth vs. falsehood is among the mental means to this end—is being destroyed.”

[Arendt 2](#)

Civilizational Progress

I have said that civilizational progress consisted of the progress of freedom and was embodied by conceptual innovations that had freed the society from crises that were stifling it, but I did not give any examples. Here are two that are not well known enough.

THE *PHYSIS* \ *NOMOS* DISTINCTION

The distinction between *physis* and *nomos* freed the conceptual environment of antiquity, enabling the Greeks to conceptualize political freedom and experiment with it by inventing democracy. Unfortunately, this freedom, as they understood it (see: [Arendt 1](#)), has all but disappeared from our conceptual environment.

The ancient Greek innovators could not have conceptualized this freedom unless the *physis* \ *nomos* distinction had first liberated their conception of the world.

“The development of rationality will have another essential consequence on social thought: the break-up of the sacred order as a global order, the awareness of the opposition between nature and culture, *physis* and *nomos*...”

The systematic reflection of intellectuals (notably the ‘sophists’ of the second half of the fifth century BC) on the journeys that Greek colonization had made possible, led them to realize that while all peoples possess the same universal physical nature (*physis*), whose laws are the same for all: eating, drinking, reproducing..., they do, however, have laws and customs (*nomoi*) that differ from those of Greece. This means that a certain variation in laws and customs according to time and place is compatible with life and that laws and customs are largely the fruit of human construction. They are not founded in nature, nor imposed by the gods; they are a reality of another kind, accessible to human action. The unique order of earlier societies, from primitive societies to the sacred monarchies of the Near East, is thus split into two orders—nature and culture.

Now, this principle of a *physis* \ *nomos* distinction—a universal *physis* that can not be touched, a variable *nomos* that can be reshaped at will—allows critical thinking to emerge: when something goes wrong with the way society works, one can make the necessary changes. So—a notable corollary—the men who propose these modifications

are not necessarily enemies (*as was previously the case in closed societies*)⁴; critical discussion is good and desirable; the community must organize this discussion, gather opinions, and finally proceed to vote since we know that there can no longer be a total consensus. The Greek city thus invented the procedures proper to political pluralism: organized public discussion, and voting (including secret ballots, unknown in Near Eastern states). [...]

from now on the state is understood as a constructed entity open to revision”

Nemo

On the left, there is a tendency to deny *physis*, by claiming, for instance, that everything is socially constructed. On the right, by contrast, there is a tendency to deny *nomos*, by claiming, for instance, that social hierarchy is entirely natural.

THE CONCEPTUAL DISTINCTION BETWEEN SIN AND CRIME

This conceptual innovation, unfortunately too little known, introduced in the 12th century by theologians such as [Peter Abelard](#) and [Peter Lombard](#), is another decisive civilizational milestone. Indeed, by explicitly distinguishing the field of morality and the field of law, the distinction between sin, which belongs to the [internal forum](#), and crime, which belongs to the external forum, not only “*provided viable rules for the unviable Christian morality*” (Nemo), but it also led directly to the church and state separation principle.⁵

(Before the introduction of this distinction) “Law and morality were then largely conflated (as they are in all traditional sacred societies, and even today in most Muslim societies). Henceforth, a distinction is made between the ‘internal forum’ and the ‘external forum’....

From now on, the state will only deal with crimes and misdemeanors. It will have no right to interfere in matters of conscience, or in private life in general.”

Nemo

Identifying the Problem

The problem is not the philosophical problem of truth, but rather the instrumental problem of lies, namely institutional lies. These are two very different problems.

Given that institutional lies, seen as invisible constraining means, are more likely to succeed in an impoverished conceptual environment, our primary goal should be to enrich it with liberating conceptual tools. It is worth noting that this action—aimed at empowering agents and expanding their freedom spaces—would operate at a higher level of abstraction than lies, which operate at the level of beliefs. Because, unlike beliefs, conceptual tools are neither true nor false. Rather, they are more or less appropriate for the tasks we want them to perform.

⁴ I clarify.

⁵ Legal historian Harold J. Berman has described what happened in the European conceptual environment in the 11th and 12th centuries as a veritable revolution. [Berman](#).

To achieve this goal we need a new type of organization—an anti-ideological one— where the qualifier “anti-ideological” would not be merely a statement of principles, but would characterize the very structure of the organization. Its design would be grounded in the acknowledgment that institutional lies can come to be regarded as indubitable truths by virtue of the performative power concentrated at the top of ideological institutions.

To design an anti-ideological institution, we must first describe what characterizes an ideological institution. This requires introducing the distinction between two types of agentive sovereignty.

Freedom and Sovereignty

“The *raison d’être* of politics is freedom,
and its field of experience is action.”

Arendt 1

If ideologies succeed in transforming the world, it is not only because they are instrumentally rational. It is also because by adhering to the dogmas, individuals that embody an ideological community inhabit a common world and form a Markov blanket. However, adherence to the dogmas requires renouncing one’s conceptual sovereignty, without having to renounce one’s executive sovereignty.

To clarify the distinction between the two types of sovereignty, let us add that, in principle, a soldier renounces his executive sovereignty (He agrees to obey orders), without necessarily renouncing his conceptual sovereignty. Which may lead him to disobey orders.

THE RELATION BETWEEN OUR SOVEREIGNTY AND OUR POLITICAL FREEDOM.

“I have said that philosophers first began to show an interest in the problem of freedom when freedom was no longer experienced in acting and in associating with others but in willing and in the intercourse with oneself, when, briefly, freedom had become free will.[...]
Men are free *politically*⁶—as distinguished from their possessing the gift for freedom—as long as they act, neither before nor after; for to *be* free and to act are the same.[...]
If men wish to be free *politically*, it is precisely *executive* sovereignty they must renounce.”

Arendt 1

In other words, in order to act at the same hierarchical level as ideological communities, we need to transfer our executive sovereignty to our organization, without, however, renouncing our conceptual sovereignty.

“...thanks to our complementary perspectives, our joint models would be richer and more accurate than any individual model.”

Friston 2

⁶ The words in italic are for clarification.

It is our organization that would enable us to act in concert at the econiche level. Once again, it is the relation between the individual and collective scales that is at work.

The fundamental *raison d'être* of our consciousness is to enable us to acquire what we need to know and to know what we need to do in order to ensure the well-being of those we love and our own well-being, but it only enables it. This means that, depending on the poverty or richness of our environment, we have to work more or less hard to become aware of what is vital, to undeceive ourselves and at the same time expand our freedom space. We can say, then, that our consciousness oversees our relation to our knowledge and our freedom. This relation depends on what we are interested in, and takes the form of the question: how do we know? Stated in the first person singular. How do we know what is true? How do we know if we are being lied to? How do we know to which extent a theory is well founded or misleading? How do we know what we should do? These questions are fundamental given the propensity for control, which has profoundly shaped the current state of our econiche.

Our answers depend on many factors, including our education, judgment, way of reasoning, temperament, experience, lucidity, our idiosyncrasie, our cultural and conceptual environment. As well as how much time we have to unravel all this.

Whereas our collective relation to knowledge, truth and freedom is subordinated to the question: how do we agree? Stated in the first person plural. How do we agree on what we consider to be true? How do we agree on which theories underpin the orientation of our collective future? And, ultimately, how do we agree on what we should do?

But to be able to agree, we need both the will and the means. We need compatible conceptions of the world, a common goal, and a deliberation space where we can debate and decide on the best ways to get closer to our common goal. This means side with the decision of the majority if consensus cannot be reached. This would require us to relinquish the corresponding portion of our executive sovereignty.⁷

An Anti-Ideology Organizational Structure

As a general rule, political institutions have a pyramidal structure that concentrates power at the apex, thereby rendering unsolvable the fundamental problem of the distribution of knowledge versus the concentration of power. This type of organization—which, for instance, gives Vladimir Putin the power to destroy humanity—derives directly from the first form of propensity for control.

To overcome the knowledge distribution problem, and achieve the second form of propensity for control—not being controlled by others without controlling them—the idea would be to establish and maintain an organizational structure approaching a [complete graph](#).

⁷ This part is reworked from *The Concept of Common Consciousness, a Tool For Countering Ideologies*, Derome D.

The Organization's Internal Model

The organization's *raison d'être* is to act on the abstract intersubjective layer of the econiche in order to enrich the conceptual environment with liberating conceptual tools. According to the free energy principle, the choice of action comes from the internal model. The founders must therefore first establish an initial common internal model. This raises the question: what requirements their internal model must fulfill in order to be rightly considered their common consciousness?

To answer this question, I propose to deepen the distinction between shared knowledge and common knowledge and try to anticipate the evolution of consciousness.

The Evolution of Consciousness

“This suggests a three-level taxonomy of consciousness: (1) arousal, or consciousness itself, which we call ‘affective consciousness’; (2) arousal of representations—that is attentional activation—which we call ‘perceptual consciousness’; (3) reflective re-representation of affective and perceptual consciousness, which we call ‘cognitive consciousness’ (Panksepp). With reference to our introductory definitions: affective consciousness is *interoceptive*, perceptual consciousness is *exteroceptive*, and cognitive consciousness is *abstracted* from them both.”

Solms

Our affective consciousness is the part of our internal model pointing inward. Our perceptual consciousness is the part of our internal model pointing outward. Our cognitive consciousness is the part of our internal model pointing toward the first two and toward itself. On the evolutionary scale, the emergence of cognitive consciousness is recent, having developed out of affective consciousness and perceptual consciousness.⁸

A kind of common consciousness could emerge from the internal model of an organization dedicated to acting in order to prevent the feared civilizational collapse.

COMMON KNOWLEDGE IS NOT REDUCIBLE TO SHARED KNOWLEDGE

[Common knowledge](#) is intersubjective, i.e., knowing that others also know what we know and that they know that we know, and so on. Shared knowledge is not: we know something that others also know, without knowing if they know it and without them knowing if we know it. We will establish that common knowledge is not reducible to shared knowledge, by showing that the transition from the second to the first can be causal.

The idea is to conceptualize common consciousness by transposing to the concept of consciousness what common knowledge adds to shared knowledge. We must therefore clarify

⁸ In [Preventing Nuclear Annihilation With the Free Energy Principle](#), I illustrate how cognitive consciousness may have emerged from affective consciousness, the propensity for control and perceptual consciousness by learning to detach (control) visual percepts—which are fundamental constituents of perceptual consciousness—from their sources in order to project the creation of increasingly sophisticated tools. For instance, in order to project the making of [hand axes](#) or [cleavers](#), they had to extend the temporal dimension of their internal model.

the conditions that enable this addition. This is not necessarily obvious. The way we are going to proceed is, let's say, a little technical, but it is essential if we want to be able to anticipate the potential that such a common consciousness could hold.

We shall proceed in two stages. We will modify Hans Christian Andersen's famous tale, *The Emperor's New Clothes*, to enable us to illustrate more clearly the transition from shared consciousness to common consciousness. Then, by solving a riddle, we will demonstrate that, under certain conditions, common knowledge is not reducible to shared knowledge.

In the case of shared perceptual consciousness, we can imagine simple scenarios—for instance, a group gathered around a campfire. Everyone sees the fire, yet perception is not intersubjective; for it to become so, it would require the addition of theory of mind, which falls under cognitive consciousness.

THE KING IS NAKED!⁹

Believing to wear clothes invisible to those who are stupid or incompetent, a king appeared naked before his court, but no one expresses the ridiculousness of the situation except a little boy who exclaims: “THE KING IS NAKED!” And the whole court erupts in laughter.

By doing so, the little boy acts on the cognitive consciousness of the king and the members of the court. He transforms the input of the calculation of the consequences, as well as its output. One can imagine all sorts of reasons why no one dares to express the absurdity of the situation—for instance, fear of the consequences, or conformism, the strategic tendency to blend into the group like a zebra into its herd. But all these reasons stem from the calculation of consequences, and thus from cognitive consciousness. The little boy does not calculate; he candidly expressed not only the absurdity of the situation, but also the strangeness of the court's silence. This has the effect that the court stops acting as if everything were normal. They stop lying and publicly and collectively expresses the ridiculousness of the situation.

Before the little boy's intervention, apart from the king, everyone knows that the king is naked, but this knowledge is not common, it is only shared since it belongs to perceptual consciousness. With his intervention, this knowledge and their calculation become common, because the little boy's public declaration has radically transformed the informational state.

THE CUCKOLDS' RIDDLE¹⁰

The idea of the proof that common knowledge is greater than shared knowledge derives from a seemingly insignificant riddle. This riddle is not really difficult to solve if you are familiar with reasoning by recurrence. But it conceals another riddle whose solution reveals something

⁹ *The Emperor's New Clothes*, Hans Christian Andersen.

¹⁰ Same as [Josephine's Problem](#), but I need the cuckold version for the role played by the institution.

profound, but invisible, about the nature of information and public speech.¹¹ It reveals the role of the institution in the relinquishment of executive sovereignty of its members, as well as the role of monosemy.

THE RIDDLE

An academy of male logicians, isolated on an island, has a rule in its constitution stating that a member who learns he is a cuckold must publicly repudiate his wife the next morning. A cuckold is crowned with a pair of horns invisible to him, but visible to everyone else. Everyone knows he's a cuckold, except himself. A second rule forbids the exchange of any information about horns and infidelity. The subject is thus absolutely taboo, nobody talks about it, and all members scrupulously respect the rules.

One day, a foreign woman is invited to give a lecture attended by all members. At the end of her lecture, she asks the audience, "Why do some members wear horns?" The next morning, everything remains normal, as it does the day after, but on the third morning, four members repudiate their wives.

THE SOLUTION

A member can only be in one of two states: either he is a cuckold, or he is not. All those in the same state share the same perspective from the point of view of relevant information. A non-cuckold sees four pairs of horns. A cuckold sees only three. So, cuckolds' reasoning is interchangeable, as is that of non-cuckolds.

Let's now take the cuckold's point of view at the end of the lecture. He must ask himself: is she only talking about the three pairs of horns I am seeing? He must then be thinking: if I am not a cuckold, the three I see will repudiate their wives the day after tomorrow, because they will be thinking, if I am not a cuckold, the two I see will repudiate their wives tomorrow (because the speaker's question uses the plural form). So when there's no repudiation the day after tomorrow, he knows that he is a cuckold. The non-cuckolds learn the good news on the third morning, because they have said to themselves: if I am not a cuckold, the four I am seeing will repudiate their wives on the third morning, because they will say to themselves: if I am not a cuckold...

THE META-RIDDLE

The trigger that sets off the members' reasoning is clearly the speaker's question. However, since they all already know that there are cuckolds among them, and they all know that they all know, and they all know that they all know that they all know, so on and so forth, the speaker seems to add no information. So, what is it that sets off the causal chain?

¹¹ This riddle nagged at the back of my mind for almost twenty-five years, until its solution came to me while watching a [video of a lecture](#) given by Steven Pinker, in which he distinguishes between the concepts of shared and common knowledges.

THE SOLUTION TO THE META-RIDDLE

First of all, note that the rules of the institution are part of the causal structure. A member is not entirely sovereign of its decisions. Some of its executive sovereignty has been yielded to the institution.

Remember that knowledge is not common if at least one member of the community does not know whether this knowledge is shared by all the other members.

The possible number of cuckolds is not shared knowledge because the non-cuckolds know that there are four or five, but don't know whether it's four or five; while the cuckolds know that there are three or four, but don't know whether it's three or four. What they know and what they don't know is different for each of them. A member does not know whether he is a cuckold or not, while all the others do. The rules and taboo ensure that the unknown remains.

The four pairs of horns are part of the perceptual consciousness of the non-cuckolds and the speaker. But they are not part of the perceptual consciousness of the cuckolds. The presence of the four pairs of horns is therefore not entirely public information. The question posed by the speaker initiates the process of the members comparing what they see with what she sees. They ask themselves, "Is she just talking about the horns I see?" The process, which lasts two days for the cuckolds and three for the others, transforms their information state. Taboos and rules prevent the exchange of relevant information. Similar to the child exclaiming: "THE KING IS NAKED!" by transgressing the taboo, the question publicly and explicitly establishes the presence of the horns. Before the question was asked, the presence of the horns was publicly perceptible, but it was not cognitively public. The question brings the "horns" into the public sphere and triggers the members' reasoning by transforming their world: from one in which the issue of infidelity is cognitively absent from the public sphere, to one in which it is cognitively present.

Here it is important to distinguish between perceptual consciousness and cognitive consciousness. On the one hand, everyone is aware of the presence of the horns because they can see them. On the other hand, the phrase "explicitly and publicly present" belongs not only to the realm of speech, but also suggests a necessary condition for common cognitive consciousness. The content of a common cognitive consciousness must be publicly shared among the members of the organization.

Prior to the speaker's question, all members privately share the same question: "Do I wear horns?" The rules of the institution require them to resolve the question. The rules, the question and the reasoning all depend on language. The causal structure upstream of repudiation does not take place entirely in the physical world; it takes place in the intersubjective world that language creates. The question creates an intersubjective unison between the members that ultimately transforms their knowledge. The exact number of cuckolds was not public information, except for the lecturer. Her question, in the particular context that dictated the members' behavior, transformed their common unknown (each member knows that every other member wonders, just like him, whether or not he is being cuckolded). On the third morning, everyone knows that there are only four cuckolds. But it was the public announcement of the presence of the horns that was the causal trigger. For, if the question had been asked privately to each of the members,

without any further information, it would have started nothing. Because the reasoning set off by the speaker's question, which begins with: "Is she talking about me too?" must be common and simultaneous. All the members simultaneously know that they are all asking themselves the same question, and are all simultaneously doing the same reasoning.

Since every member knows that there are horns, it seems as if the speaker cannot add anything to it, but there is indeed something that triggers and leads to repudiations, something invisible and abstract. So the common knowledge induced by the public statement of the question transcends the shared knowledge, because the private statements of the question would not trigger the process.

This highlights the conditions that a common cognitive consciousness must meet if the concept is to be useful, coherent and justified : an institutional condition where the members of the organization agree to follow the rules that will enable them to constitute their common knowledge and work in concert toward their common goal. As well as a communicational condition: in order to understand one another, propositions must be monosemic, their epistemic grounds and pragmatic reasons must be both communicable and actually communicated. In this way, the organization's internal model could constitute their common conception of the world—one that could justifiably be seen as their common consciousness emerging from the pooling of the relevant contents of their cognitive consciousness.

Conclusion

“ The opposition of thinking and acting, which, depriving thought of reality and action of sense, makes both meaningless. ”

Hannah Arendt

When we say: “*thanks to our complementary perspectives, our joint models would be richer and more accurate than any individual model*” [Friston 2](#), it's just half of the story. And that's not even the most important half. Models are important insofar as they allow us to get closer to our goal. With this new type of organization, if we work well, I believe that our joint action could be historically relevant.

In short, the institutional innovation proposed here aims to free us as much as possible from the control that History exerts over us, by concretizing, at the collective level, the second form of the propensity for control—not being controlled by others without controlling them—for and by those who choose to embody it.

References

- Albarracín, Constant, Friston, Ramstead. *A Variational Approach to Scripts*.
- Arendt 1. *What Is Freedom ?* In *Between Past and Future*.
- Arendt 2. *Truth and Politics*.
- Arendt 3. *What Is Authority ?* In *Between Past and Future*.
- Berger & Luckmann. *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*.
- Berman. *Law and Revolution, The Formation of Western Legal Tradition*.
- Friston, Thornton, Clark. *Free-Energy Minimization and The Dark-Room Problem*.
- Friston, Parr, Heins, Constant, Friedman, Isomura, Fields, Verbelen, Ramstead, Clippinger, Frith. *Federated Inference and Belief Sharing*.
- Geary. *The Origin of Mind: Evolution of Brain, Cognition, and General Intelligence*.
- Nemo. *Histoire des idées politiques dans l'Antiquité et au Moyen Âge*.
- North. *Five Propositions about Institutional Change*.
- Panksepp & Solms. *The “Id” Knows More than the “Ego” Admits: Neuropsychanalytic and Primal Consciousness Perspectives on the Interface Between Affective and Cognitive Neuroscience*.
- Pinker. *How Progressives Define “Right Wing”*.
- Ramstead, Constant, Badcock, Friston. *Variational Ecology and the Physics of Sentient Systems*.
- Solms & Friston. *How and Why Consciousness Arises: Some Considerations From Physics and Physiology*.